

ENHANCING THE INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE RESISTANCE OF LAMINATED COMPOSITES BY USING CONTINUOUS CARBON NANOTUBE FILMS

Hong Xu^{1,2}, Xiao Tong^{2,3}, Yongyi Zhang², Qingwen Li², Tsu-Wei Chou⁴ and Weibang Lu²

¹School of Materials Science and Engineering, Shanghai University
99 Shangda Road, BaoShan District, Shanghai, 200444, China
Email: hxu2014@sinano.ac.cn

²Division of Advanced Nano-Materials, Suzhou Institute of Nano-Tech and Nano-Bionics, CAS China,
Ruishui Road, Suzhou Industrial Park, Suzhou, 215123, China
Email: wblv2013@sinano.ac.cn, yyzhang2011@sinano.ac.cn, qwli2007@sinano.ac.cn

³ Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Nanjing University of Science and Technology
Xiaolingwei 200, Nanjing, 210094, China.
Email: xtong2014@sinano.ac.cn

⁴Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Delaware
126, Spencer Lab, Newark, Delaware, 19716, United States
Email: Chou@udel.edu

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ABSTRACT

To enhance the weak interlaminar interactions, continuous carbon nanotube (CNT) films synthesized using floating catalytic chemical vapor deposition method were interleaved between the neighboring layers in the laminate composites. The CNT film was directly deposited on the carbon fiber preregs with the film thickness under well control. The as-synthesized CNTs were characterized using transmission electron microscope, and the microstructure of CNT films and CNT/carbon fiber hybrid composites were characterized using scanning electron microscope. A preliminary study of the flexural properties was implemented through the three-point-bending testing, and found that thin CNT film interleaving could improve the flexural strength and modulus of the laminate composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

During the last few decades, fiber reinforced composites (FRCs) have being extensively used in many fields such as aerospace, defense, marine, power generation and sports[1], and their end use is further expanded with time. Normally, FRCs are fabricated by laying up a series of thin lamina, which is a kind of thin film consisting of high performance fibers and the matrix materials. The high mass-specific modulus and strength of fibers, wide variation of fiber/matrix materials properties, as well as the great controllability of the stacking sequence make the FRCs of light-weight, high structural performance and excellent in designability, which eventually endows their wide applications.

It is well recognized that between adjacent laminar of laminate composites there always exists a thin matrix-rich layer where the matrix is not reinforced and experiences high stress concentration, resulting in poor through-thickness properties of the composites[2]. Besides, the interlaminar shear stresses is usually higher due to mismatch of anisotropic mechanical and thermal properties of the neighboring plies. Both intrinsic limitations make the laminate composites be susceptible to delamination along interlaminar planes under loading, especially in laminates subjected to compression, impact and fatigue loading. Several approaches have been developed to reinforce the through-thickness direction, particularly the interface or interlaminar region, such as 3D-textiles,

stitching, and z-pinning using micro-sized fibers[3-5]. However, these treatments usually result in an unavoidable reduction of in-plane mechanical properties due to in-plane fiber volume loss and/or fiber damage or misalignment during z-direction insertion.

In this respect, a wealth of research efforts have been devoted to reinforce the thin interlaminar places by using a thin layer of high performance nanofibers, as illustrated in Fig. 1[6]. The main role of nanofibers is to reduce the stress concentration due to mismatch of ply properties, typical of multidirectional laminates, as well as to bond the adjacent plies without increasing the composite weight and the laminate thickness. To date, electrospun polymeric nanofiber is the most often used materials after the pioneer work from Dzenis and Reneker[7]. Researches have shown that electrospun polymeric nanofibers offer great potential in enhancing the delamination resistance, impact resistance, damping, flexural strength, and fatigue properties of laminated composite materials[8-10]. It has been found that the thickness of the nanofiber film greatly affected its reinforcement[8]. Specifically, there is a thickness threshold, below which the incorporation of nanofibrous sheets either had no effect or it increased the flexural strengths, the flexural modulus and interlaminar shear strength of the laminated composites, while above the thickness threshold value all the measured mechanical parameters worsened due to the reason that the thick electrospun nanofibrous sheet can't be completely impregnated in the matrix and form an even weaker places in the composites. A more detailed overview of this research area can be found in a review article authored by Zucchelli et al. [11].

Fig. 1. A schematics of nanofiber interleaved laminate composites[6].

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have shown great promise for reinforcing polymers due to their superb mechanical and physical properties[12]. The strength and modulus of CNTs are much higher than those of existing electrospun nanofibers, implying their potential application in reinforcing the composite interlaminar performance of laminate composites. Moreover, CNTs are electrical and thermal conductive and stable at temperature up to 400°C in air. Thus, enclosing CNTs will not only enhance the structural performance, but also enable multifunctional characteristics of fiber composites. An et al.[13, 14] developed the hierarchical composite structures by electrophoretic deposition of CNTs onto both carbon fiber and glass fiber fabrics prior to the infusion of epoxy resin. It has been found that CNT coating could effectively enhance the interlaminar shear strength, fracture resistance, as well as the electrical conductivity of the laminate composites. The preparation of high quality CNT dispersion is one of the major challenges of this treatment[15]. To use the dry CNTs as the interlaminar reinforcement, Wardle and coworkers [16, 17] have hybridized vertical CNT array and horizontal aligned CNT films made by rolling down CNT arrays between the fabrics to enhance the mechanical and electrical properties of the fiber composites. Obviously, the CNT arrays should be synthesized first and then transferred to the fabric surfaces. Most recently, by inserting a layer of Wang et al[18], integrated carbon nanotube (CNT) thin films of 10-15µm thick into carbon fiber prepreg composites to create hybrid composite materials with high CNT content, and found the tensile properties decreased with the increase of CNT contents, but the electrical conductivity exhibited significant improvements. The decrease of the tensile properties might be that the CNT film used is so thick that weaker layers are formed in the composites.

Here, we develop a novel approach to *in situ* coat continuous CNT films onto the carbon fiber preregs before laying them up for curing. CNT films are synthesized using the floated catalyst chemical vapor deposition method, and are directly wound onto the carbon fiber prepreg sheets near the outlet of the furnace. The thickness of the CNT film is well controlled from nanometer to micrometer scales. The microstructure of the hybrid composites, and the effects of the CNT film thickness on the flexural properties of laminate composites have been studied.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials

The unidirectional T700/ YPH-120-23A/B epoxy prepreg was supplied by Yixing Hengya Carbon Fiber Technology Co., Ltd. The areal density of the prepreg is 150g/m² and the fiber content is 60%. Prepreg was cut into rectangular pieces of 0.16×0.96m²(6.3×37.8in²), and then wound onto a round collector which is usually used for collecting CNT films.

The continuous CNT films were made using a proprietary floating catalytic chemical vapor deposition method. As described in Ref[19], ethanol was used as the carbon source, in which 0.23 to 2.3 weight percent (wt %) ferrocene and 1.0 to 4.0 wt % thiophene were dissolved. The solution was then injected at 0.08 to 0.25 ml/min from the one end of the furnace into a hydrogen carrier gas that flowed at 400 to 800 ml/min, with the furnace hot zone in the range of 1050° to 1200°C (Fig. 2). In the high temperature zone, ferrocene forms the iron nanoparticles that act as nucleation sites for the growth of nanotubes, and the thiophene is an established rate enhancer for CNT growth. A sock-like CNT aerogel of high degree of mechanical integrity was formed in the furnace. The CNT aerogel can then be captured and wound continuously out of the hot zone as a fiber or film[19]. In this study, the continuous CNT films were collected by the carbon fiber prepreg covered collectors, as illustrated in Fig. 2. The thickness of the CNT films coated on the prepreg was controlled by the collecting time. In this study, the duration of 1min, 2min, and 5min were adopted to evaluate the CNT film thickness effect on composite flexural properties.

Fig. 2. Schematics of collecting CNTs films onto the prepreg.

Fig. 3. Typical curing process used for composite laminates manufacturing.

Table 1 Dimensions of three-point-bending test specimen.

Collection time (min)	pristine	1	2	5
Length L(mm)	46.80	48.24	49.14	50.4
Width b(mm)	5.20	5.36	5.46	5.60
Thickness h(mm)	2.60	2.68	2.73	2.80

The CNT film coated carbon fiber prepreg was cut into $0.08 \times 0.08 \text{m}^2 (3.1 \times 3.1 \text{in}^2)$ slices, and then stacked in the sequence of $[0]_{24}$. The laminates were hot-pressed following the curing process shown in Fig.3. The dimension of the three-point bending test samples were summarized in Table 1.

2.2. Characterization

The structure of individual CNTs was characterized using transmission electron microscope (TEM), Tecnai G2 F20 S-TWIN. The morphology of the CNT films and the cross section of the hybrid laminate composites were characterized using the scanning electron microscope (SEM), Hitachi S4800. The flexural strength and modulus of the laminate composite were evaluated in terms of three-point bending tests according to the ASTM D790-10[20] standard, using Instron 3365 with the load cell of 5000N.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1 Microstructures of hybrid composites

Fig. 4 shows the microstructures of CNT films deposited on the carbon fiber prepreg at low and high resolutions. It can be clear seen that CNTs are randomly distributed within the film, and the film is of high porosity (Fig. 4a), which is critical for the resin impregnation. TEM analyses found that the as-grown CNTs had a diameter of 20-30nm with 5-12 walls, as shown in the insert of Fig. 4b for example. The diameter and thickness of the nanotube can be controlled by modifying the processing conditions.

Fig. 4. Structure and morphology of CNTs and CNT film.

Fig. 5. The SEM images of fiber laminates with interleaved CNTs films of (a) 1min, (b) 2min, and (c) 5min deposition.

The cross-sections of the CNT film interleaved carbon fiber laminate composites were characterized using SEM image analysis. Fig. 5 shows the cross-sections of composites with different CNT collection time. It can be found that with increasing collection time, the thickness of the CNT interleaves increases, which are about 2.77 μm , 3.09 μm , and 11.68 μm for 1min, 2 min, and 5min collecting of CNTs, respectively. This is consistent with the increasing thickness of laminates summarized in Table 1.

3.2 Flexural properties of hybrid composites

The flexural response of CNT interleaved carbon fiber laminate composites were evaluated using three-point-bending tests following the standard ASTM D790-10. As shown in Fig. 6a, the flexural modulus of the hybrid composite increased slightly with increasing content of CNTs in the case of 1, 2, and 5min collection. As shown in Fig. 5, the thin rein area between the neighboring layers was reinforced by the continuous CNT film, which is the main reason of the flexural modulus improvement.

The flexural strength of the hybrid composite increased with the collection time of CNT films in the range of 1min to 5mins, as shown in Fig. 6b. It is interesting to note that the 1-2 minutes of CNT film collection can effectively increase the composite flexural strength, while no obvious further enhancement was observed with more CNT interleaved.

Fig. 6. Mechanical properties of the laminate composites: (a) flexural modulus, (b) flexural strength.

4. Conclusions

In this study, we have developed a novel method for fabricating continuous CNT film interleaved carbon fiber composites, aiming to improve the interlaminar properties of laminate composites. The continuous CNT film was made through the floating catalyst chemical vapor deposition method and coated layer-by-layer onto the surface of carbon fiber prepreg directly. The thickness of the interleaved CNT layer can be well controlled from nanometer to micrometer, or even larger scales. A preliminary study of the flexural properties were implemented, and found that thin CNT film interleaving could improve the flexural strength and modulus of the laminate composites. A systematic study of the structural and functional performance of CNT film interleaved laminate composite is undergoing. Compared with the existing CNT interleaving technology, this new processing is quite simple, easy for scalable, and highly controllable, which may advance the development of CNT based high performance and multifunctional composites.

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